

GROWTH TREND OF COTTON CULTIVATION IN KARNATAKA: AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The study analyses about the growth trend in area, production, and yield of cotton in India as well as Karnataka State. Cotton is an important crop for the sustainable economy of the country and livelihood security of the community Indian Cotton Farming. It is cultivated was 312 lakh hectares across the global level and in around 117 lakh hectares in the country. Thus, India accounts for around 37.5 per cent of the global cotton area and contributes to 26 per cent (i.e 6.20 Million Tonnes) of the global cotton produce of 23.92 Million Tonnes. Cotton continues to enjoy a pre-eminent and the most favored fiber status among the Indian textile mills, as the major raw material for the textile industry. The textile industry, which consumes the cotton, as its principal raw material, contributes about 4% to the GDP and is the major exchange earner for the country. Hence, growth and development of cotton and cotton based textile industry has a vital bearing on the overall development of the Indian economy. This study mainly focused on present status of area, production and yield under cotton. Further, article revealed that the development programmes for improvement in productivity of cotton and skill developments for cotton cultivators in India as well as Karnataka State.

Keywords: *Present Scenario of Cotton Area, Production, Yield, Development Programmes and Skill Developments*

Introduction

Cotton cultivation plays a very important role in the Indian economy by providing sustainable development, substantial income and employment generation and contribution of livelihood security to millions of marginal and small farmers; such as enterprise has to be knowledge-based and market driven and needs to evolve continuously through innovations in frontier sciences to break yield and quality barriers for satisfying present and future national needs and attaining international competitiveness with larger spin-off benefits of the country. Presently, nearly 60 million people depend on cotton cultivation, marketing, processing and exports for their livelihood. India is also the only country in the world that grows not only the four cultivated species of cotton but also their intra-and-inter-specific hybrids on a commercial scale. Cotton cultivation is the most important commercial crop contributing about 75 per cent of total raw material needs of textile industry and cotton and textile exports account for good share of Foreign Exchange earnings of Rs.70,000 crores in the country. India has achieved major breakthrough in cotton yarn exports besides increasing its international market share in cotton textiles and apparels.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To study the current status of cotton cultivation in India.
2. To examine the present scenario and growth trend of cotton cultivation in Karnataka.
3. To analyse the development programmes for improvement in productivity of cotton and skill developments for cotton cultivation farmers.

Methodology of the Study

The study is mainly based on secondary sources compiled from official websites of various Departments. The data pertains to area; production and yield of cotton were collected from Directorate of Economics and Statistics in Karnataka, Ministry of Agriculture, Cotton Corporation of India Ltd., Ministry of Textiles and All India Co-ordinated Cotton Improvement Project. The time series data were collected for the period from 2000-01 to 2017-18. The study is used statistical tools for Percentage, Average Growth Rate (AGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR).

Cotton Area, Cultivation and Production in India: Present Scenario

Cotton provides direct and indirectly livelihood to 6 million agriculture farmers and about 40 to 50 million farmers are employed in cotton trade and its processing. At present, about 60 million peoples are involved directly and indirectly in cotton cultivation, production, processing, textiles, and others activities in our country. About 14 per cent of industrial production and GDP contributed of 4 per cent by the textile sector. This sector is the second largest provider of employment after agriculture sector. This industry is expected to growth from the present about US\$ 70 billion to US\$ 220 billion by 2020. During 2016-17, despite lower area coverage, higher productivity of cotton has resulted in a higher production level about 33.09 million bales (of 170kg each), i.e., an increase of 3.09 million bales, as compared to 30.01 million bales during 2015-16 in the country. India got first place in the global in cotton area with around 105 lakh hectares are under cotton cultivation i.e. around 35 per cent of the World area of 296 lakh hectares. About 62 per cent of India's Cotton is produced on rain-fed areas and 38 per cent on irrigated lands. During 2017-18, India's cotton productivity is estimated at 523.83 kg/ha. The area, productivity and yield of cotton in India for the last 10 years are as follows in Table-1.1.

Table 1.1 Area, Production and Yield of Cotton in India (2007-08 to 2016-17)

Year	Area (Hectare)	Production (Million Tonnes) (In Million Bales of 170 kg each)	Yield (Kg/Hectare)
2007-08	94.14	25.88	467.00
2008-09	94.07	22.28	524.13
2009-10	103.10	23.94	502.91
2010-11	112.35	24.02	512.95
2011-12	121.78	33.00	512.32
2012-13	119.77	34.22	525.13
2013-14	119.60	35.90	565.72
2014-15	128.19	34.80	493.77
2015-16	122.92	30.01	459.16
2016-17	108.45	33.09	540.80
2017-18	122.35	37.07	523.83
Total	1246.72	334.21	5627.72
CAGR	2.44	4.54	0.41

Source: Annual Report (2017), Various reports of Cotton Corporation of India, Government of India.

Graph 1.1 Area, Production and Yield of Cotton in India (2007-08 to 2016-17)

Economic Development and Cotton Development

Cotton is produced over around 105 lakh hectares with an annual yield of around 351 lakh bales (170 kgs of each bale) in the country. The cotton sector is the second most developed sector in the textile industry and cotton production in the country is about 18 per cent of the world production that makes it the second largest cotton cultivating country after china. This sector generates huge employment generation for both the skilled and unskilled labour, thereby contributing to strengthen the India’s economy.

Table Major States of Cotton Development in India 2018

Sl.No	States	Cotton Production (Lakh Bales)
1	Gujarat	125.00
2	Maharashtra	85.00
3	Telangana	50.00
4	Karnataka	28.00
5	Andhra Pradesh	27.00
6	Haryana	25.00
7	Madhya Pradesh	18.00
8	Rajasthan	17.00
9	Punjab	14.00
10	Tamil Nadu	5.00

Source: Annual Report (2017), Various reports of Cotton Corporation of India, Government of India.

Graph-1.2 Largest Cotton Producing States in India 2018

Use of Bt. Cotton Hybrid Seeds - Comparison of Inter-States

Bt. Cotton is the most important only transgenic crop approved in our country for commercial cultivation sector. The Genetic Engineering Appraisal Committee (GEAC) of the Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change is the nodal agency for grant of authorization for environmental release of Bt. Cotton hybrids under the Environment Protection Act, 1986 in India. Nowadays, about 1400 Bt. Cotton hybrid seeds are available for cultivation in the country. These Bt. Cotton hybrids are grown in ten States like Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Haryana, Punjab and Rajasthan. The area under Bt. Cotton has increased from 29073 ha in Kharif 2002 to 85.29 lakh hectares (81% of total cotton area) during 2016-17.

Present Growth Trends of Cotton Cultivation in Karnataka Scenario

Cotton is the major commercial crop of the state. At presently, Karnataka is the fourth largest producer of cotton in the country. Karnataka is known to produce around 7 per cent of the cotton in

the country. Cotton cultivated mostly in the valley of the plateau of North Karnataka. The climate and soil are perfect for the growth of cotton in this place. The area that lies under the cotton plantation is around 7 lakh hectares. The districts in which cotton is cultivated mostly are Dharwad, Gulbarga, Ballari, and Belagavi (As per report of Cotton Corporation of India, 2018). In Karnataka, mainly hybrids and high yielding varieties are cultivated in the districts like Raichur, Bagalkot, Vijayapura, Ballari, Dharwad, and Belagavi under irrigated conditions. While, rainfed cotton (with Assured rainfall) is predominantly grown in Dharwad, Belagavi, Shivamogga, Mysuru, and Karwar. There are various schemes in operation in the State for development of cotton. The comprehensive cotton development scheme is covering the entire State.

Area, Production and Yield of Cotton in Karnataka

The area, production and yield under cotton in the year-wise growth trends are presented in Table-1.2. It is clear from the table that there was a wide fluctuation over the years in the cotton area in the State from 2000-01 to 2017-18. During 2000-01, area under cotton was 5.25 lakh hectares which increased to 5.65 lakh hectares during the 2017-18. But in this very wide fluctuated for all the years in the State. The CAGR for the area under cotton is 2.46 per cent.

Table-1.2 Area, Production and Yield of Cotton in Karnataka (2000-01 to 2017-18)

Year	Area (In Lakh Hectare)	AGR	Production (Million Tonnes)	AGR	Yield (Kg/Hectare)	AGR
2000-01	5.25		8.55		277	
2001-02	6.08	15.8	6.12	-28.4	180	-35.0
2002-03	3.93	-35.4	3.31	-45.9	151	-16.1
2003-04	3.17	-19.3	2.65	-19.9	149	-1.3
2004-05	5.22	64.7	6.25	135.8	214	43.6
2005-06	4.13	-20.9	5.85	-6.4	253	18.2
2006-07	3.76	-9.0	5.36	-8.4	255	0.8
2007-08	4.03	7.2	7.05	31.5	313	22.7
2008-09	4.09	1.5	8.25	17.0	361	15.3
2009-10	4.57	11.7	7.05	-14.5	276	-23.5
2010-11	5.48	19.9	12.18	72.8	398	44.2
2011-12	5.70	4.0	12.03	-1.2	378	-5.0
2012-13	4.95	-13.2	10.38	-13.7	375	-0.8
2013-14	6.62	33.7	18.78	80.9	508	35.5
2014-15	8.75	32.2	23.12	23.1	735	44.7
2015-16	6.91	-21.0	20.56	-11.1	670	-8.8
2016-17	5.07	-26.6	18.00	-12.5	604	-9.9
2017-18	5.65	11.4	19.00	5.6	572	-5.3
Total	93.36		194.49		6668.23	
CAGR	2.46		10.50		8.65	

Source: Annual Report (2017), Profile of Agriculture Statistics Karnataka State (2017), Bengaluru: Department of Agriculture in Karnataka. Note: AGR-Average Growth Rate, CAGR-Compound Annual Growth Rate, Production in Million Bales of 170 kg lint.

Graph-1.2 Average Growth Rate of Cotton Area, Production and Yield in Karnataka from 2001-02 to 2017-18

The Table-1.2 and Graph-1.2 shows that the cotton production and yield in Karnataka in terms of million tonnes and kg/ hectares, Average growth rate and compound growth rate of both cotton production and yield from the period of 2000-01 to 2017-18. The production under cotton was 19.00 million tonnes (In bales of 170 kg lint) during 2017-18 as compared to 8.55 million tonnes (In bales of 170 kg lint) during 2000-01 and in this same year production which decreased to 5.36 million tonnes (In bales of 170 kg lint) during 2006-07. During the 2007-08, production under cotton was 7.05 million tonnes (In bales of 170 kg lint) which increased to 12.18 million tonnes (In bales of 170 kg lint) in 2010-11. And then it was decreased to 10.38 million tonnes (In bales of 170 kg lint) in 2012-13. And it was which increased to 18.78 million tonnes (In bales of 170 kg lint) and 19.00 million tonnes (In bales of 170 kg lint) during the periods from 2013-14 to 2017-18 respectively. The CAGR for the production under cotton was 10.50 per cent.

The yield performance of cotton in Karnataka over the years is presented in Table-1.2. It could be observed from the table that there was a fluctuation in the yield of cotton in Karnataka, which was 277 kg/ha in 2000-01, has decreased to 255 kg/ha in 2006-07, then it increased to 370 kg/ha in 2015-16, and again it decreased to 572 kg/ha in 2017-18.

Development Programmes for Improvement in Productivity of Cotton and Skill Developments for Best Cultivator's Practices:

1. Implementation of High Density Planting System Programme

The objective of High Density Planting System (HDPS) programme is to improve cotton productivity in the country as well as State so that research work being done in the field of productivity improvement could be transferred from lab to field level and the productivity of cotton in the country as well as State could be improved.

2. Inter-Cropping System

Keeping in view climatic vulnerability, market fluctuation and better resources use to produce higher economic return and yields per unit area, intercropping system is useful for increasing input use efficiency. It offers greater stability in production and meets the domestic needs of the farmer and provides suitable distribution of farm resources.

3. Efforts to Implement Instrument Based Quality Evaluation System

In India, cotton is traded in market yards in the form of kapas at the farmers' level. Generally, the assessment of quality of kapas (i.e. grade/colour, fibre length, strength, fineness, moisture contents etc.) are done in the market yards where kapas are either stored on the platforms or carts/trolley by visual inspection and hand testing at the time of auction.

4. Integrated Cotton Cultivation (ICC)

With a view to benefit the cotton farming community on the one hand by way of making available quality inputs like seeds, pesticides etc., for producing quality cotton and to enable the user industry (i.e. textile mills) to obtain desired quality of cotton on the other, the Govt. of India has

promoted Integrated Cotton Cultivation(Contract Farming), which has the involvement of corporate sector not only in extension services but also in making available quality inputs like seeds, fertilizers etc., to the farmers to improve productivity and quality of Indian cotton.

5. Front Line Demonstrations under MM-II of TMC

The Government of India, besides, States, ICAR, Krishi Vigyan Kendras, State Agricultural Universities and various other organisations had identified CCI, as one of the Nodal Agencies for implementing Front Line Demonstrations (FLDs) under Mini Mission II of Technology Mission on Cotton.

6. Improvement of Coloured Cotton

Government of India and State Government are making efforts to encourage cultivation of colour cotton in the country with the active cooperation of the Industry, supplemented by R&D. There has been much progress in research in recent years on coloured cotton. Presently coloured cotton is being cultivated in small area in Dharwad (Karnataka), Coimbatore (T.N.), Vidharbha (Maharashtra) and Guntur (AP).

7. Up-gradation of Skills for Ginning & Pressing

Efforts are being made for Up-gradation of Ginning and Pressing machines with modern and latest technology to achieve better quality of lint cotton. Besides this, operators' skills are also being up-graded through proper training to handle the machines with latest technology.

Sustainability for the Cotton Cultivation Sector

In the country's conditions under which cotton cultivation is grown and the issues associated with its cultivation fluctuate very due to differing environmental, agro-ecological, climatic, socio-economic, and political conditions for the cotton cultivators. These, fluctuating conditions refer that the cultivation of the same crop may result in the significantly various practices/ impacts, and that there are significantly several options and capabilities available to address these impacts. In Karnataka, impacts of cotton cultivation growing, and development of the better options for managing impacts, should therefore always be done with reference to the specific Karnataka context. However, despite these highly variable conditions, and the site-specific nature of appropriate responses, the impacts of cotton growing are often considered in the State. Both the cotton industry and cotton as raw materials are assessed either generically, or on the basis of the averaging of information from different countries without reference to the specific production locations.

Impacts of cotton production have been the establishment of development schemes and initiatives working with cotton cultivation farmers to ensure the sustainability of growing cotton sector. Development programmes promoting sustainable intensification of agriculture to jointly protect and enhance the livelihoods of cotton producers and the environment have long been working in the cotton sector. In recent years, there has been an emergence of initiatives aimed at promoting sustainability in cotton production that involve the downstream supply chain for cotton. This is evident with large retailers who have a growing interest in improving their own overall footprint and who seek to provide customers with greater confidence in the honesty of their products. As a result, there are an increasing number of production and systems that claim to promote the objectives of sustainable farming to improve cotton sector in the State at particulars.

Conclusion

It may be concluded that, Cotton is produced in the country in around twelve states. There has been self-sufficiency when it comes to fabrication and clothing in India because cotton is produced in excess in this country. India has an extremely suitable climate that helps in the cotton production. It can be expected that within a few years, India will become the largest producer in the country. Given below is a list of the top ten largest cotton producing states in India. Apart from these initiatives, there have been development programmes launched for the development of the cotton industry like supply of certified seeds, water management, improved processing, and availability of clean and modernized factories, encouraging organic cultivation, cultivator education, and other services as required or demanded by the cotton cultivators. The cotton sector with many other programmes and schemes is trying to increase its production to meet the projected requirement of the textile industry and also aims to strengthen the economy by increasing quality export of cotton in Karnataka economy.

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